

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL CONTENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS OF THE 6TH GRADE THROUGH EDUCATIONAL ASSIGNMENTS

Ashirboyeva Nafisa Aminboyevna

Independent researcher of the National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan named after Nizami
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Annotation: This article presents and analyses the scientific views of linguists, methodologists, educators, and psychologists on the importance of mother tongue education, the scientific and theoretical substantiation of educational tasks in developing students' pragmatic competence during the lesson, the development of their communication skills, educational tools that help develop pragmatic competences, work on the text, and the consistent improvement of logical thinking skills, and expresses a subjective attitude to them.

Keywords: native language lessons, pragmatic competencies of students, types of educational tasks, linguistic and methodological aspects, speech-pragmatic knowledge, Uzbek literary language norms, communication, logical thinking ability, communication skills, working on the text, contextual approach, oral and written speech, subjective attitude.

Today, in native education, goals of methodological and pedagogical importance are set to solve the urgent problems of developing pragmatic competencies of students of general secondary education through educational tasks. In the textbook of the famous methodologist D.N. Yuldasheva "Methodology of teaching the Uzbek language (based on a cognitive-pragmatic approach)", interesting, non-standard tasks, game tasks, educational tasks, creative, creative-practical tasks are compiled and put into practice. "The cognitive-pragmatic method of education, which aims to form a creative thinker, requires the teacher to deviate from the textbook as much as possible in the educational process and to use a system of textbook educational materials, topics similar to the topics planned in the program, and related topics and educational tasks." "Pragmatic competence is the ability to skillfully navigate specific situations. Pragmatics is interpreted as a real communication situation that involves the selective use of linguistic means to solve communicative tasks." Pragmatic competence is understood as the essence of participation in the communication process, taking part in it, while adhering to the speech etiquette of the speaker and listener. For the improvement of pragmatic competence, the product of verbal communication, meaningful logical thinking and a cognitive-contextual approach developed from

the past is of great importance. In general, the development of pragmatic competence in the education system is one of the continuous and complex processes. In order for 6th grade students to develop their pragmatic competences through educational tasks in native language lessons, they should be directed to work on information and texts that cover the sum of disciplines and interdisciplinary integration in order to form a mature person. In the native language textbooks for students of general secondary schools, which are put into practice, knowledge and understanding of the content of texts related to the development of pragmatic competences are given, exercises and tasks, texts related to the development of individual-intellectual, speech-cognitive, communicative-pragmatic, communication competencies.

The 6th grade “Mother Language” textbook contains educational exercises and control exercises, which play an important role in the development of students' pragmatic competencies. This textbook also provides text-based tasks, which guide students to communicate correctly and meaningfully. In this regard, V. Zayeskova's point of view is noteworthy. In her opinion, “learning tasks and exercises constitute the “extratextual component” of the textbook structure. Working on learning tasks is one of the contextual processes.” Also, the main part of the tasks given in mother tongue textbooks is given in a way related to working on the text.

In general, in order for students to read the text, understand it, independently determine the idea in the text, and at the same time express their opinions on the content of the text in a logical and subjective way, the teacher must organize the lesson based on creativity. In each organized lesson, it is important to pay attention to the students' ability to speak fluently and express their opinions freely based on logic. *In particular, in the current 6th grade “Mother Tongue” textbook, interactive questions such as “What do you think of when you think of a hospital?”, “Which doctor did you see?”, “What are the names of the rooms where patients are admitted to a hospital?”, “What words and phrases are most often used in a doctor’s speech?” will give positive results in teaching them how to go to the hospital, which doctor to contact when they get sick, and how to use the right words in the communication process.” It is important to have basic communication skills and abilities to solve patient problems. These include, first of all, talking to the patient, getting into his inner world, adequately understanding the individual psychological characteristics of the patient, and others.* The ability to overcome these and many other difficulties that every medical worker faces every minute is the main feature of the psychology of communication between a doctor

and a patient. The purpose of communication between them is the provision of medical care by one of the participants in the communication to the other. With good communication with the doctor, the treatment used has a good effect, has much fewer side effects and complications. There are, of course, certain conditions for communicating with the patient. Only after the doctor has studied the probable diagnosis of the patient's illness, his personality, profession, social conditions, level, worldview, level of knowledge, external psychological signs, and has spiritually prepared himself for this communication, does he have the moral right to communicate with him¹. V.N. Komissarov noted that three types of pragmatic relations are involved in speech communication. First, these are pragmatic relations expressed through the source of information (transmitter, speaker or writer), such a pragmatic relation includes the purpose of the transmitter of information, his personal attitude to the transmitted information and the planned effect on the receptor. The second type of pragmatic relation is expressed in the text (thought, sentence), which contains the pragmatic meaning expressed by the linguistic unit. The third type of pragmatic relation is the pragmatic relation of the person receiving the information (receptor, listener, reader) to the information perceived through the text. Such a relation is reflected in the process of perceiving information, in his attitude to this information or its transmitter. The communication between the speaker and the interlocutor is based on a certain cognitive analysis of certain information, and abstract aspects are clarified. In the process of communication, along with analytical functions, a synthesis of secular and cultural knowledge, as well as the expression of attitudes, is also carried out. The scientist-teacher, first of all, models the mother tongue lessons in an integrative content based on the main goal;

- designs the lessons based on modern advanced methods and innovative technologies;
- develops and implements in practice a set of special, non-standard educational exercises and tasks in addition to the educational tools in the textbook when teaching the topics specified in the curriculum;
- takes into account the students' ability to master the topic and develop speech and pragmatic growth when performing the educational tasks given in the textbook "Mother Language";

¹ Olimjonova Z.B. Shifokor va bemor o'rtasidagi muloqot psixologiyasi. Tashkent Medical Academy Integration of Science, Education and Practice in Modern Psychology and Pedagogy: Problems and Solutions. Volume 4 | TMA Conference | 2023.826b

- implements a strategic structure for working with students with the text and its types.

If 6th grade students are taught to use the opportunities of native language lessons effectively and appropriately, and if systematic methodological work is carried out on this topic, and their pragmatic competencies are developed based on established requirements, the sections on working on scientific, artistic, official, discussion texts, as well as questions and assignments provided in the textbook will ensure that students' speech skills grow. Therefore, especially homework assignments require guidance based on objective and subjective factors that influence the development of pragmatic competencies in students. This increases their development of pragmatic competence, self-development, and self-awareness.

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